

INCREASING INTEREST IN CLASSICAL MUSIC BASED ON GENDER APPROACH OF UNIVERSITY SCHOOL TEENAGERS

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Abstract: The article provides information on the importance of our national classical music in the education of the young generation, the problems of their attitude to classical music in the current era, and the implementation of the process of forming the interest of teenagers in classical music based on the gender approach in the general education school.

Key words: interest in classical music, gender approach, music culture lesson, teenagers, extracurricular activities of teenagers.

It is known from the history of the past that the ancient and rich musical culture of the Uzbek people has been a powerful source of spirituality for centuries. Therefore, the treasure of our traditional music, which combines national values with wonderful traditions, has not lost its artistic and aesthetic value. The golden treasures of the world of Uzbek classical music are endless and one of the oldest in the world. These immortal classical works have been performed by professional and amateur musicians and singers among our people, passed from centuries to centuries, from teachers to students, perfected, polished and enriched, and have survived until our time and became the priceless property of our people.

Uzbek classical music has been shown as an example of seriousness and great spirituality. Therefore, these music samples should be studied not only as a form of creativity and art, but also as an important part of culture. Uzbek classical music is so broad that it is rare to find topics that it does not cover. The people were able to instill in their songs, epics, statuses and musical instruments the educational themes that can influence the spiritual development of a person. Through these music samples, the people expressed their heartaches, love, romantic experiences, and dreams.

The main goal of providing excellent information about Uzbek classical music is to contribute to the education of secondary school students in the spirit of Uzbek musical traditions and values. The tasks of the science of music culture are to create information about the songs and great songs created by our people and their representatives, epics, statuses and instrumental tunes of various forms, as well as their performance methods and methods.

Our modern society is in the conditions of commercialization of musical culture, which leads to the loss of the values of our national classical music, its depth and meaning. Nowadays, most of the teenagers prefer pop music. Children who have a positive attitude to classical music are mainly students of music schools and educational institutions specializing in additional music. At the same time, the musical interests of boys and girls are quite different. While girls prefer modern pop songs performed mainly by popular youth groups, boys prefer more aggressive trends in modern pop genres such as rock, rap and other similar genres. This is due to the fact that the connection of adolescents with music, as a rule, occurs spontaneously and uncontrollably outside the walls of high school. By playing computer games using modern gadgets (phones, tablets, players, etc.), they play music that accompanies the plots of the games and is used as ringtones (voice alerts, alarms, etc.). experience pressure. An important source of filling the musical experience of teenagers is the Internet, in which the main place is social networks ("Telegram", "Facebook", "Instagram", "Twitter", "Tiktok", "You tube", etc.). occupies

Pedagogically mechanizing the process of formation of interest in classical music among teenagers in a general education school is an effective tool that ensures the creation of conditions for increasing the level of interest in classical music among teenagers. There are no appropriate models and technologies for the formation of interest in classical music among teenagers based on the gender approach in the general education school, the justification of this process is devoted to this article.

Teenagers interested in classical music can be divided into the following categories:

- level of interest (low level) - characterized by a short-term, superficial emotional reaction of adolescents to bright parts of classical music works; knowledge of individual interesting, interesting details of the biographies of classical composers, but weak activity in musical activities, in which the performance of creative tasks is carried out only with the help of a teacher;

- level of curiosity (medium level) - long-term emotional empathy of teenagers when listening to classical music works, understanding of the impressiveness of the musical image, knowing the representatives of certain periods of classical music; manifestation of creative activity, in which pedagogical correction is carried out only in individual situations;

- stable level of interest (high level) - characterized by the need for adolescents to get emotional pleasure from working with classical music works

and to analyze deep, meaningful works of world classical art; the ability to analyze the means of musical expressiveness (characteristics of the rhythmic pattern, timbres of musical instruments, genre characteristics); research activity expressed in the independent search for high artistic works of classical music on the Internet and sharing it in social networks among peers and the teacher.

It is necessary to determine the initial level of formation of interest in classical music among teenagers in general education school, to further eliminate gender conflicts in music lessons and extracurricular activities, to determine the musical interests of teenage girls and boys.

Based on the gender approach in the general education school, three stages of the process of formation of interest in classical music among teenagers can be described: emotional, intellectual, activity.

The goal of the first stage (emotional) is to stimulate the emotional attitude of teenagers to classical music. At this stage, taking into account the musical preferences of boys and girls, adolescents have a short-term emotional reaction to bright parts of classical musical works. At the same time, teenagers will get basic knowledge about interesting, interesting details of biographies of classical composers. It is desirable to get acquainted with musical activities in the performance of creative tasks performed with the help of a teacher, which ensures that teenagers reach a level of interest (low level).

The goal of the second stage is to help enrich the knowledge of (intellectual) teenagers in the field of classical music. In the second stage, we will introduce teenagers to the impressiveness of the musical image, during which they will gain knowledge about the representatives of some periods of classical music. Using a gender approach allows you to choose biographical facts that are interesting for girls (love experiences, romantic moments of life) and boys (heroic actions, creating works that have begun to be used in sports games in modern sound). When listening to classical music, the emotional empathy of adolescents becomes deeper and longer. If necessary, the manifestation of creative activity, which is corrected by the teacher, increases, which ensures the achievement of the level of interest (average level).

The goal (activity) of the third stage is to activate the independence of teenagers in understanding classical music. In this, we focus on increasing the research activity of teenagers who get emotional pleasure from communicating with classical music works and develop the need to communicate with deep, meaningful works of world academic art. Joint music lessons and extracurricular activities allow the teacher to create musical and creative activities in which

girls and boys participate equally. They also develop the ability to analyze the means of musical expressiveness (characteristics of the rhythmic pattern, timbres of musical instruments, genre characteristics), which leads to independent search for high artistic works of classical music on the Internet and sharing it between peers and the teacher on social networks. Achieving a sustainable level of interest in adolescents (high level).

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